

PHYTOHORMONE-LIKE EFFECT OF PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES ON THE VEGETATIVE GROWTH OF HARICOT BEAN (*PHASEOLUS VULGARIS* L.)

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Abstract

The phytohormone-like effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives on the vegetative growth of haricot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) was studied. For this purpose, haricot bean plants were grown from seeds treated with synthetic compounds at a concentration of 10^{-6} M during the vegetative stage. The effect of synthetic compounds on the growth of haricot bean plants was compared with the effect of phytohormone auxin IAA (1H-indol-3-yl)acetic acid) used in a similar concentration of 10^{-6} M. The control haricot bean plants were grown from seeds treated with distilled water. The morphometric parameters (average length of shoots and roots (mm), average number of roots (pcs)), and biochemical indicators (content of photosynthetic pigments ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) - chlorophylls a and b, as well as carotenoids) of haricot bean plants were determined. The effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives on the vegetative growth of haricot bean was similar to the effect of auxin IAA. The morphometric parameters of 2-week-old haricot bean plants treated with synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives exceeded similar parameters of control plants: average length of shoots – by 16.98 – 105.66 %, average length of roots – by 105.88 – 288.24 %, average number of roots – by 31.82 – 284.09 %, respectively. The morphometric parameters of 2-week-old haricot bean plants treated with auxin IAA exceeded similar parameters of control plants: average length of shoots - by 86.79 %, average length of roots – by 182.35 %, average number of roots – by 161.36 %, respectively. The cytokinin-like effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives on the biosynthesis of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean plants was also studied. The content of photosynthetic pigments ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean plants treated with synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives exceeded similar parameters of control plants: chlorophyll a - by 14.25 – 121.07 %, chlorophyll b - by 3.38 – 145.11 %, chlorophyll a+b - by 15.47 – 85.34 %, carotenoids - by 5.53 – 165.88 %, respectively. The content of photosynthetic pigments ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean plants treated with auxin IAA exceeded similar parameters of control plants: chlorophyll a - by 34.65 %, chlorophyll a+b - by 22.9 %, carotenoids - by 50.98 %, respectively. The plant growth-regulating effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives depended on their chemical structure. The selected most biologically active synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives are proposed to be used as new plant growth regulators of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.).

Keywords: *Phaseolus vulgaris* L., auxins, cytokinins, pyrimidine derivatives, plant growth regulators.

Introduction. Bean (*Phaseolus spp.* L.) is one of the oldest and most important grain legumes in the world, consumed both as a vegetable (as leaves, pods and immature seeds) and as a mature grain [1]. Total bean production is over 23 million metric tons, of which 7 million metric tons are produced in Latin America and Africa. Bean seeds are enriched with 20-25 % dietary proteins, among which phaseolin is the main storage protein, vitamin biotin, a high content of minerals, including more than 26 such as iron, phosphorus, magnesium, manganese, zinc, copper, calcium and others, thanks to which beans provide 10-20 % of an adult's need for a number of nutrients and minerals [1 - 3]. Although low in methionine and cysteine, dried bean seeds are a valuable source of the amino acids lysine and tryptophan, which are lacking in maize, rice or other cereals [2]. Bean seeds also contain anti-nutritional factors, including α -amylase inhibitors, arcelins, tannins, lectins, phenolics, and phytates, which have therapeutic properties in the prevention of breast and

colon cancer through their antioxidant properties, as well as in lowering cholesterol and other lipids due to their presence in high-fiber diets [1, 2].

An important task of modern agriculture is the development of new effective plant growth regulators of grain legume bean (*Phaseolus spp.* L.). Today, fertilizers and natural bio-regulators are widely used to improve the growth and development of bean plants during the growing season, increase their productivity, and improve adaptation to abiotic and biotic stress factors [4, 5]. Nevertheless, a very promising approach is the creation of new plant growth regulators based on synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives, which are able to exhibit physiological effects similar to plant hormones auxins and cytokinins, improving seed germination, the formation and growth of plant shoots, roots and flowers, enhancing photosynthetic processes in plant leaves [6, 7]. Currently, new synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives such as

Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) are used as new environmentally friendly plant growth regulators to improve crop productivity and increase their adaptation to abiotic stress factors [8 - 11]. At the same time, screening of plant growth regulators among new synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives, is carried out. Our previously published work [12] showed that synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives at a concentration of 10^{-7} M revealed an auxin-like effect on the rooting of isolated (separated from the roots) stem cuttings of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya. The results of this work confirmed the perspective of the practical use of synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives to improve the vegetative propagation of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) and other plant species of the family Fabaceae by stem cuttings.

The purpose of this work is to study the regulatory effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine de-

rivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives at a concentration of 10^{-6} M on the vegetative growth of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya. These studies will contribute to the further development of new effective growth regulators used in agriculture to improve the growth and development and increase the yield of haricot bean plants.

Materials and methods. The synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7) were synthesized at the Department for Chemistry of Bioactive Nitrogen-Containing Heterocyclic Compounds, V.P. Kukhar Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry and Petrochemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. The plant growth-regulating effect of pyrimidine derivatives was compared with the effect of auxin IAA (1*H*-indol-3-yl)acetic acid) manufactured by Sigma-Aldrich, USA (Table 1).

Table 1.

Chemical structure, name and relative molecular weight of auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7)

Chemical compound	Chemical structure	Chemical name and relative molecular weight (g/mol)
IAA		1 <i>H</i> -indol-3-ylacetic acid MW=175.19
Methyur		Sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine MW=165.17
Kamethur		Potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine MW=181.28
1		2-ethylsulfanyl-6-methylpyrimidin-4-ol MW=170.23
2		6-methyl-2-propylsulfanyl-pyrimidin-4-ol MW=184.26

3		2-benzylsulfanyl-6-methylpyrimidin-4-ol MW=232.31
4		2-isopropyl-6-methyl-pyrimidin-4-ol MW=152.20
5		Sodium salt of 4-hydroxypyrimidine--2-thiolate MW=149.14
6		2-methylsulfanylpyrimidin-4-ol MW=142.18
7		2-benzylsulfanylpyrimidin-4-ol MW=218.28

Seed treatment and plant growing conditions.

The seeds of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya were sterilized with 1 % KMnO₄ solution for 15-20 min, then treated with 96 % ethanol solution for 1 min, after which they were washed three times with sterile distilled water. After this procedure, seeds were placed in the plastic cuvettes (each containing 10 – 15 seeds) on the perlite moistened with distilled water (control sample) or water solutions of IAA or synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives at a concentration of 10⁻⁶M (experimental samples). Then seeds were placed in the thermostat for their germination in darkness at the temperature 23 °C during 48 h. After the emergence of sprouts, they were placed in a climatic chamber in which seedlings were grown for 14 days at the 16/8 h light/dark conditions, at the temperature 23 - 25 °C, light intensity of 3000 lux, and air humidity 60 - 80 %. Comparative analysis of morphometric parameters of haricot bean plants (average length of shoots and roots (mm), average number of roots (pcs)) was carried out at the end of the two-week period according to the method [13].

Statistical processing of the experimental data, performed in triplicate, was carried out according to the Student's t-test with a significance level of P≤0.05; mean values ± standard deviation (± SD) [14].

Determination of the content of photosynthetic pigments.

To perform the extraction of photosynthetic pigments, we homogenized a sample (500 mg) of haricot bean leaves in the porcelain mortar in a cooled at the temperature 10 °C 96 % ethanol at the ratio of 1: 10 (weight: volume) with addition of 0,1-0,2 g CaCO₃ (to neutralize the plant acids). The 1 ml of obtained homogenate was centrifuged at 8000 g in a refrigerated centrifuge K24D (MLW, Engelsdorf, Germany) during 5 min at the temperature 4 °C. The obtained precipitate was washed three times, with 1 ml 96 % ethanol and centrifuged at above mentioned conditions. After this procedure, the optical density of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoid in the obtained extract was measured using spectrophotometer Specord M-40 (Carl Zeiss, Germany).

The content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids was calculated in accordance with formula [15, 16]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cchl a} &= 13.36 \times A_{664.2} - 5.19 \times A_{648.6}, \\ \text{Cchl b} &= 27.43 \times A_{648.6} - 8.12 \times A_{664.2}, \\ \text{Cchl (a + b)} &= 5.24 \times A_{664.2} + 22.24 \times A_{648.6}, \\ \text{Ccar} &= (1000 \times A_{470} - 2.13 \times \text{Cchl a} - \\ &97.64 \times \text{Cchl b}) / 209, \end{aligned}$$

Where,

Cchl – concentration of chlorophylls ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), Cchl a – concentration of chlorophyll a ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), Cchl b – concentration of chlorophyll b ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), Ccar – concentration of carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$), A – absorbance value at a proper wavelength in nm.

The chlorophyll and carotenoids content per 1 g of fresh weight (FW) of extracted from haricot bean leaves was calculated by the following formula (separately for chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and carotenoids):

$$A_1 = (C \times V) / (1000 \times a_1),$$

Where, A_1 – content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, or carotenoids (mg/g FW),

C - concentration of pigments ($\mu\text{g/ml}$),

V - volume of extract (ml),

a_1 - sample of plant tissue (g).

The content of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids (%) determined in the experimental haricot bean leaves was calculated according to similar parameters determined in the control haricot bean leaves.

Results and discussion. As is known, plant hormones auxins together with cytokinins play a key role in seed germination and subsequent formation of shoots and roots in the vegetative stage of plants [17 - 19]. This work is aimed at studying the auxin-like and cytokinin-like regulating effects of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7, listed in Table 1), used at a concentration of 10^{-6}M for seed treatment, on the vegetative growth of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya.

The data obtained in this work indicate that the effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives (listed in Table 1) on the vegetative growth of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya was similar to the effect of auxin IAA. Improvement in growth and development of roots and shoots of haricot bean plants was observed within 2 weeks compared to control plants (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The effect of auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7) at a concentration of 10^{-6}M on the vegetative growth of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya compared to control plants

The morphometric parameters of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya treated with synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives exceeded similar parameters of control plants and were similar to the parameters of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya treated with auxin IAA (Figures 2 - 4).

The parameters of the average length of shoots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants statistically significantly increased: by 86.79 % - after treatment with IAA, by 94.34 % - after treatment with Methyur,

by 70.75 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 41.51 – 105.66 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 2). The synthetic compounds № 3 and 7 showed lower effect, parameters of the average length of shoots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants statistically significantly increased by 16.98 – 21.71 %, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The effect of auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7) at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$ on the average length of shoots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris L.*) variety Bilozernaya compared to control plants

The parameters of the average length of roots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants statistically significantly increased: by 182.35 % - after treatment with IAA, by 235.29 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 229.41 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 229.41 – 288.24 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 1, 5, 6 and 7, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control haricot bean

plants treated with distilled water (Figure 3). The synthetic compounds № 2 and 4 showed lower effect, parameters of the average length of roots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants statistically significantly increased by 105,88 – 123.53 %, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The effect of auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7) at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$ on the average length of roots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris L.*) variety Bilozernaya compared to control plants

Synthetic compound № 3 showed a lesser effect, the parameters of the average length of roots (mm) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants increased by 11.76 %, but did not differ statistically significantly from those of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 3).

The parameters of the average number of roots (pcs) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants statistically significantly increased: by 161.36 % - after treatment with IAA, by 245.45 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 200 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 154.55 –

284.09 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 1, 4, 6 and 7, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 4). The synthetic compounds № 2, 3 and 5 showed lower effect, the parameters of the average number of roots (pcs) of 2-week-old haricot bean plants statistically significantly increased by 31.82 – 88.64 %, respectively, compared to similar parameters of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The effect of auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7) at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$ on the average number of roots (pcs) of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya compared to control plants

Summarizing the obtained data, it should be noted that synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives: compounds № 1, 4, 5, 6 and 7 showed the highest effect, while synthetic compounds № 2 and 3 showed less effect on the morphometric parameters of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya.

Similar results were obtained in our previously published work [12] in which synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1, 4, 5 and 7, listed in Table 1) at a concentration of $10^{-7}M$ showed the highest auxin-like effect on the rooting of isolated (separated from the roots) stem cuttings of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya. Based on the obtained results, it is proposed to use these synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives as new substitutes for auxins to improve the vegetative propagation of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) and other plant species of the family Fabaceae by stem cuttings.

As is known, cytokinins are involved in the control of chloroplast differentiation and the biosynthesis of photosynthetic pigments, which are the main indicators of plant productivity [15, 16]. This work investigated the cytokinin-like effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives (listed in Table 1) at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$ on the biosynthesis of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya.

The content of chlorophyll a ($\mu g/ml$) statistically significantly increased: by 46.38 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 55.16 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 31.06 – 121.07 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 5, 6 and 7, respectively, compared to similar indicators of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 5).

The content of chlorophyll b ($\mu g/ml$) statistically significantly increased: by 110.45 % - after treatment

with Methyur, by 145.11 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 9.32 – 101.23 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 5 and 6, respectively, compared to similar indicators of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 5).

The content of chlorophylls a+b ($\mu g/ml$) statistically significantly increased: by 66.87 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 83.93 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 53.5 – 85.34 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 5, 6 and 7, respectively, compared to similar indicators of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 5).

The content of carotenoids ($\mu g/ml$) statistically significantly increased: by 15.77 % - after treatment with Methyur, by 19.2 % - after treatment with Kamethur, by 5.53 – 165.88 % - after treatment with most active synthetic compounds № 5, 6 and 7, respectively, compared to similar indicators of control haricot bean plants treated with distilled water (Figure 5).

The auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives № 1, 2, and 4 at a concentration of $10^{-6}M$ were found to be less effective in terms of the content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya.

The content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean plants treated with synthetic compounds № 1, 2, and 4 statistically significantly exceeded the similar parameters of control haricot bean plants: chlorophyll a ($\mu g/ml$) - by 14.25 – 26.57 %, chlorophyll b ($\mu g/ml$) - by 3.38 – 23.1 %, chlorophylls a+b ($\mu g/ml$) - by 15.47 – 19.23 %, carotenoids ($\mu g/ml$) - by 23.24 – 24.98 %, respectively (Figure 5).

The content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean plants treated with auxin IAA statistically significantly exceeded the similar parameters of control haricot bean plants: chlorophyll a ($\mu g/ml$) - by 34.65 %, chlorophyll a+b ($\mu g/ml$) - by 22.9 %, carotenoids ($\mu g/ml$) - by 50.98 %, respectively (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The effect of auxin IAA and synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new derivatives (compounds № 1 – 7) at a concentration of 10^{-6} M on the content of chlorophylls a and b, as well as carotenoids ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya compared to control plants

At the same time, synthetic compound № 3 did not have a stimulating effect on the content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of 2-week-old haricot bean plants, which were not statistically significantly different or were slightly lower than those of control plants (Figure 5).

Thus, the obtained results confirmed the cytokinin-like effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new most active derivatives (compounds № 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 and 7) at a concentration of 10^{-6} M to increase the content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of haricot bean plants.

Analyzing the relationship between the chemical structure and biological activity of new synthetic derivatives of pyrimidine, compounds № 1, 4, 5, 6 and 7, it can be assumed that the high auxin-like and cytokinin-like effects of these compounds is associated with the presence of substituents in their chemical structure: compound № 1 contains an ethylthio group in position 2, a hydroxyl group in position 4 and a methyl group in position 6; compound № 4 contains an isopropyl substituent in position 2, a hydroxyl group in position 4, and a methyl group in position 6; compound № 5 is the sodium salt of 4-hydroxypyrimidine-2-thiolate; compound № 6 contains a methylthio group in position 2 and a hydroxyl group in position 4; compound № 7 contains a benzylthio group in position 2 and a hydroxyl group in position 4 (Table 1).

At the same time, the decrease in auxin-like and cytokinin-like effects in synthetic compounds, pyrimidine derivatives № 2 and 3 can be explained by the presence of substituents in the chemical structures of these compounds: compound № 2 contains a propylthio group in position 2, a hydroxyl group in position 4 and a methyl group in position 6; compound № 3 contains a benzylthio group in position 2, a hydroxyl group in position 4 and a methyl group in position 6 (Table 1).

It is possible to assume that the high plant growth regulating effect of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new most active derivatives (compounds № 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 and 7), is explained by their auxin-like effect on the proliferation, elongation and differentiation of plant cells, which are the main processes of the formation and development of shoots and roots of haricot bean plants, as well as the biosynthesis, metabolism and signaling of endogenous auxins in plant cells [17 - 24].

Probably, the increase in the content of photosynthetic pigments in the leaves of haricot bean plants is related to the cytokinin-like effect of the investigated synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives on increasing the synthesis and slowing down the degradation of chlorophylls and carotenoids in plant cells [25, 26].

Conclusion. The obtained results indicate the prospect for the practical use of synthetic compounds based on pyrimidine derivatives: Methyur (sodium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine), Kamethur (potassium salt of 6-methyl-2-mercapto-4-hydroxypyrimidine) and their new most active derivatives (compounds № 1, 2, 4, 5, 6 and 7) at a concentration of 10^{-6} M for improving the growth and development of haricot bean (*P. vulgaris* L.) variety Bilozernaya during the vegetative stage and increasing the content of photosynthetic pigments in plant leaves that ensure plant productivity.

Statement of Conflict of Interest.

The authors are declared that they have no conflict with this research article.

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